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RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BATUMA****FIRST NAME: DEAN****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MS Word -Office 365 on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Academic Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-11)
2. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2021, 12)
3. American versus British English Language (EUCLID, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Chicago Manuel of Style (EUCLID 2021, 43-56)

Commented [GK1]: Be uniform in citing a particular source in the same paper. This was not how you referenced the course pack in the body of the paper. Kindly make everything uniform

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING-EUCLID REQUIREMENTS

1) INTRODUCTION

After EUCLID settled the administrative obligations to start my EUCLID DIPH (Ph.D. in International Public Health), I received orientation documents followed by the opening course ACA-401/ACA-401D. There were video tutorials on using Zotero step by step, accessible from the CMS/LMS (Course Management System/Learning Management System). The goal was to teach me the basics of academic work, scholarly writing, and research. I had to jump into the water and start swimming in the ocean of meandering academic obligations at the highest level, and I have found it interesting so far because I still have a lot to learn.

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As a caveat, this paper, response paper in EUCLID jargon, is an overall assessment of the material. More precisely, my road map is to discuss an overview of the main concepts I am interacting with from the ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1) Revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck & Dr. Kabiru Gulma 2021. Using the first person singular, I will focus on essay writing, plagiarism, Chicago Manual of Style

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(CMS) Crib Sheet, American versus British English Language, and essential insights on some basic writing rules. In the following, I will refer to this course as “ACA-401D.”

2) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

It has given me discover that the ACA-401D introductory course invites me to think differently about writing academic papers. As I have found in this introductory course, the ground rules for writing papers are an opportunity I must seize to double my efforts to become a better scholar and writer.

The course gives excellent suggestions I want to follow each time I write my papers. One of the critical steps is that my documents must critically assess an essential aspect of one of the theories I will discuss scientifically: the thesis of my paper will necessarily be stated at the beginning while saying what that aspect is (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 13).

I will make sure that my first step is to write short sentences, avoid long paragraphs, and take care to indicate transitions. However, as a rule, I should only quote a passage if the passage plays a significant role in the article or if I believe, with substantial supporting evidence, that there is controversy about whether the philosophical thinker had the opinion that I attribute to him.

Applying these basic guidelines will require that I spend enough time editing my writing after I have written the first draft. My papers for this course will be better than they would be, and I will eventually start editing as I write. I understand that the ACA-401D opening course is the precursor to so many valuable preparation tools that await me to report better with clarity, conciseness, and above all, without ever committing the academic crime of plagiarism.

3) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH LANGUAGE

It is worth remembering that "American and English are two variations of World English. This way, they are more comparative than various, particularly with 'taught' or 'logical' English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25). Although the two types of English might appear comparable from the start, I should never forget to pay attention to one thing of utmost importance in distinguishing the two versions of English. I agree with the assertion that no one can fail to note differences in vocabulary, grammar, spelling, punctuation, pronunciation, dates, times, expected usage, and other things one should constantly keep in mind” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25-27).

From the above, I have learned that at EUCLID University, one should not use the two versions interchangeably. Instead, I must decide which version to use first and use it throughout my paper. I promise to follow all these excellent guidelines and focus all my efforts on cultivating myself.

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4) PLAGIARISM

I take very seriously what constitutes plagiarism and the unacceptable use of third-party texts. I believe telling your readers where you found information is essential to the writing process. "Plagiarism is when the author uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34)." I recognize that originality is the spearhead against plagiarism and abusive paraphrasing. Euclid recommends that the hard work of others be recognized and honored each time the student submits their essay and that anyone other than the student write the paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 43). Along the same lines, avoiding plagiarism also lets readers know that your information is trustworthy.

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Therefore, I understand that the key to avoiding plagiarism is correctly citing the author or source who provided the information you are using. However, too many citations will make your article look bad. Therefore, it should be rewritten or paraphrased when the time comes. "Paraphrases are the ideas an author has produced on a subject but written down in his works" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021).

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5) CHICAGO MANUEL OF STYLE (CMS) CRIB SHEET

I have found that EUCLID endorses the Chicago (Turabian) rules and provides invaluable templates and guidelines for paper formatting (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24).

I learned that EUCLID recommends Chicago-style inline citations, also known as author-date style, which uses the writer's last name, year of publication, and page number referenced in parentheses ([The University of Chicago, 2017](#)). I am aware that this style uses in-text citations in parentheses to let readers know that they can refer to the list of references at the end to find the full authority of information from the indicated source. Ultimately, I agree to abide by EUCLID's expectations for using Turabian-style rules unless otherwise specified.

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I concur that when formatting a reference list, one should include all cited sources and follow specific guidelines. Some of them are centering the title at the top of the page, arranging entries alphabetically by author's last name, spacing each entry with a blank line between entries, and ensuring that each entry has a half-inch hanging dash.

6) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

I must recognize that until the last minute of my [Euclid University](#) entrance process, I felt like getting to grips with the protocols of a Ph.D. course, coupled with a lot of learning, unlearning, and relearning, was probably going to be a journey of uncountable risks.

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Reading and re-reading ACA-401D has given me hope and courage to keep going, and I believe I can get through this journey well. I was impressed with the number of resources available to help me succeed. As I know, all academic essays attempt to provide answers to hypotheses to communicate evidence-based information. There is a whole process to follow. Among other things, I must be sure I am defining and analyzing the task, creating initial plans, collecting related resources and credible academic sources, and above all, sifting through a critical reading (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021).

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In other words, I understand that what [Euclid University](#) mentioned above has a deep meaning. While reading, I realized it is crucial to underline or highlight relevant information and always keep my essay's topic in mind. I will firmly commit myself to it.

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Moreover, after reading and researching, I should write an essay outline to help me understand how to answer questions and structure my essay. The opening move should be to write the first draft of my paper. I pointed out that all academic essays must include references. The ACA-401D course pack emphasizes how to query and understand the [EUCLID University](#) reference style.

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7) CONCLUSION

I am particularly impressed with how [Euclid University](#) structures and handles special tools for developing academic essays. I am optimistic that with the assigned faculty, the momentum and the road to success are on my side. I will ensure that my essay is formatted as correctly as my instructor expects the work to be well presented, and I will ensure that I fully meet the requirements.

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The future directions for this opening course will be to continue interacting with the course pack, review tutorial videos, reflect on guidance materials, do any required research, and most importantly be attentive and in constant consultation with my instructor.

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REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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The University of Chicago. 2017. "The Chicago Manual of Style Online." Accessed September 20, 2022. <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org>.

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<https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B>Deleted: "The Chicago Manual of Style, 17th Edition."
n.d.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.